

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE RIDDLES WITH METAPHORS

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ЗАГАДКИ С МЕТАФОРАМИ

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Abstract

As a means of passing knowledge from one generation to another riddles represent a very early means of literary expression. They served a definite function in rites associated with numerous events in the life of society. Riddles are generally short, puzzle-like poems in which the reader is invited to identify an object, which is described in a mysterious and sometimes playful way. *The article focuses on to analyze riddles based on metaphor.* Metaphor is the vital feature of riddles. The image is often stated as a metaphor. Metaphors give a riddle an ambiguity that derives from the juxtaposition of different things, or from a paradox, or more widely an unrealistic latent image.

Аннотация

Как средство передачи знаний от одного поколения к другому, загадки представляют собой очень ранние средства литературного выражения. Они выполняли определенную функцию в обрядах, связанных с многочисленными событиями в жизни общества. Загадки - это, как правило, короткие стихотворения, похожие на головоломки, в которых читателю предлагается идентифицировать объект, который описывается таинственным, а иногда и шутивным образом. Статья посвящена анализу загадок на основе метафоры. Метафора - важнейшая черта загадок. Образ часто называют метафорой. Метафоры дают загадке двусмысленность, происходящую из сопоставления разных вещей, или из парадокса, или, в более широком смысле, из нереалистичного скрытого образа.

Keywords: definition, question, riddle, riddle metaphors, folklore, genre, metaphorical expressions, figurative language

Ключевые слова: определение, вопрос, загадка, загадочные метафоры, фольклор, жанр, метафорические выражения, образный язык

Riddles were some of the earliest types of poetry in the English language. In England its known history begins with the Anglo-Saxons, who enjoyed composing complex riddles in verse. Riddles became an important element of art expression development, the formation part of observation, quickwittedness and systemic views on the world.

Riddles being one of the oldest and richest genres of folklore are valuable treasure of word reflecting the history, spiritual values, customs and traditions of the people in themselves.

A riddle can be a question or a statement that solicits clever or unique answers to "solve" it. In a literary sense, riddles are considered to be part of the folklore genre, as entire works of folklore can sometimes be riddles. Riddles are also considered to be rhetorical devices, as they use figurative language (i.e. pun, euphemism, metaphor).

The study of metaphor has a long literary tradition. Folklore, though a relatively new discipline, has also demonstrated a concern with figurative language in oral tradition. Until fairly recently, however, metaphor has not been the subject of extensive

treatment by linguists. Because our arguments are based on the assertion that the code is the central issue in riddling, and linguistics is the discipline most directly concerned with the code, this recent scholarship, though lacking in some regards, is central to our understanding of those riddles that employ metaphor as a block element. [5]

Few genres have such a long tradition, both oral and written, as the riddle. Different types of riddles have continued to interest people from one era to the next, because they are a voyage into the unknown. They are an invitation to embark on an adventure that either brings delight, amusement and gratification at discovering the right answer, or humiliation and vexation at being led astray. [1]

Riddles often involve metaphorical or poetic comment. This indeed was pointed out long ago by Aristotle when he remarked on the close relation of riddles to metaphorical expression: "Good riddles do, in general, provide us with satisfactory metaphors: for metaphors imply riddles, and therefore a good riddle can furnish a good metaphor". [2]

Alive without breath

As cold as death
 Never thirsty
 Always drinking
 Dressed in armor
 Never clinking – *A fish*

Kovecses states that a metaphor is a mental process in which one domain of knowledge is understood in terms of another. Metaphors have a source domain (B) which is the physical, basic and uncomplicated accessible entity and a target domain (A) which is more abstract and a less accessible entity. Therefore, a metaphor is a symbolic language system in which an indirect connection is made between two dissimilar things that have something in common. [4]

According to Cruse metaphors are part of figurative language. The meaning communicated by use of a particular word or phrase differs from the linguistically encoded or literal meaning assigned by the grammar. A metaphor induces the audience to view a thing, a person or a process as being like something else by applying the former linguistic expressions which are normally employed in references to the latter. Therefore, a metaphoric riddle is far from the literal one and require cleverness and careful thinking as well as context and relevance theoretic procedure in order to arrive at the correct riddle referent. [3]

A metaphor is similar to a simile. But a simile is a comparison between two dissimilar objects using a word like *as* or *like* to connect them. For example, if you say, “my boyfriend is *like* a watermelon in the summer,” you are creating a simile that compares your boyfriend with a watermelon. If on the other hand you are mad at your boyfriend and say, “he’s *like* a typhoon in the house,” you’re comparing your boyfriend with a typhoon.

Round *like* the moon, white *as* lime, they make me milk, and I do not tell you anymore! – *Cheese*

A metaphor compares two dissimilar objects without using a word like *as* or *like*. If you write, “my boyfriend is an angel” or “my motorcycle is a bomb on wheels,” you are creating metaphors.

The **riddles with metaphors** allow us to understand certain concepts and understand the similarities that exist between some elements.

He has no feet, yet travels far; literate, but no scholar he; no mouth, yet he clearly speaks. If you know him, you are wise. What is he? – *A letter*

Metaphors give a riddle an ambiguity that derives from the juxtaposition of different things, or from a paradox, or more widely an unrealistic latent image. Riddle metaphors cannot be forced into a single scheme by comparing them unequivocally to the metaphors of, say spoken or poetic language;

I am born and I die without ceasing;
 I still nonetheless exist
 and, without leaving my bed, I always find myself running. The answer is *the river*.

Metaphors sometimes give human attributes to objects which is the proof of personification – a type of metaphor. This riddle represents that case when affirming that the river is born, dies and runs.

A riddle may have a rhyme structure and uses a metaphor to stimulate referential memory;

Thousands of years ago we have transported man;
 now he takes us hidden in the engine of their cars. The answer is *the horse*.

That is to say, in the abovementioned riddle *the horse* is naturally associated with the image of the man being carried on his shoulders. But motor horsepower is not an association that occurs naturally. This second clue is not understood through instinctive knowledge, but through prior knowledge.

A riddle metaphor differs from a poetic or standard-language one, for riddles do not have the leeway of poetic language. But nor are riddle metaphors as readily comprehensible as metaphorical expressions in the standard language, the descriptive power of which we do not always even notice.

What has roots as nobody sees, is taller than trees,

Up, up it goes, and yet never grows?
 The answer is “*mountain*.”

But in what sense does a mountain “go” up? Only in our experience of it – it seems to rise up before us, but does not actually rise. So its “going” is metaphorical, and if we try to think of things that really travel upward, we will fail to guess the riddle. This is a common block in many riddles: it’s hard to tell what is literal and what metaphorical. When trying to guess this riddle, one has to go through each descriptive element and wonder if it is a literal description or a poetic metaphor.

What runs without legs? – *A cloud*

If a riddle has only one or two words linked metaphorically (such as a cloud running legless), the latent image seems simple. On hearing the question, the riddlee cannot, however, know which of the latent-image elements are metaphors and which should be taken literally.

In spring I am gay in handsome array;

In summer more clothing I wear;
 When colder it grows I fling off my clothes;

And in winter I quite naked appear.
 – *A tree*.

In this riddle the seasonal shedding of a tree’s covering is expressed in terms of a human being’s disrobing.

I am within as white as snow, without as green as herbs that grow;

I am higher than a house, and yet am lesser than a mouse. – *Walnut on a tree*

Old Mother Twitchett had but one eye, and a long tail which she let fly;

And every time she went over a gap, she left a bit of her tail in a trap. – *Needle and thread*

Though of great age, I’m kept in a cage,

Having a long tail and one ear, my mouth it is round,

And when joys do abound, O, then I sing wonderful clear. – *Bell in a steeple*

I have a cock on yonder hill I keep
him for a wonder
And every time the cock do crow,
It lightens, hails and thunders. – *A gun* [6]

These four riddles contains a particularly neat example of an extended metaphor. Extended metaphors are metaphors developed through more than one point of comparison: 'And every time the cock do crow, / It lightens, hails and thunders.' This riddle compares the firing of a gun to a cock that produces lightning (the flash), hail (bullets) and thunder (the report) when it crows.

What has teeth but cannot eat? – *A saw*.

What has a tongue and can't talk?
– *A shoe*.

Many eyes and never a nose, one tongue, and about it goes. – *A shoe*.

In these riddles we find the metaphorical extension or comparisons. They are based on metaphor.

There is something with a heart in its head. – *A peach*

This example is built on the comparison of various physical features of a peach to anatomical structures of an animal. [5]

These riddles represent indisputable metaphorical riddles. In each some quality of a specific object is compared to a similar quality of a different object. Metaphorical riddles are irreplaceable in the development of thinking:

"The little red cock runs along the neck" – *Fire*

Solving such riddles is deciphering metaphors. Penetrating into the hidden meaning of the metaphor, the guesser must compare, compare objects or phenomena from different, often distant areas, see features of similarity in them, highlight them, refer them to one semantic category and, on the basis of this, determine what was conceived, solve a logical problem. Solving metaphorical riddles develops both figurative and logical thinking.

Riddles are a genre in which ambiguity is acceptable at all levels of language. They favour metaphors the purpose of which is both to mislead the listener and to bring to light a new aspect of a thing, an object or an action that is as a rule highly familiar to all. They demonstrate that two linguistic categories that are from one perspective different are in fact similar when viewed in another light.

Riddle metaphors cannot be forced into a single scheme by comparing them unequivocally to the metaphors of, say, spoken or poetic language. The scale of expression in riddles is a wide one, ranging from creative invention often improvised on the spot via extremely worn or commonplace metaphors to images the meaning of which has become completely obscure.

Analysing metaphors has not been easy for researchers, even though metaphor is the vital feature of riddles. Models have been developed for determining the structure of riddles and the metaphors used in them, but they often use only a small corpus of material, and attempts have then been made to fit the model to the classification of larger materials.

Metaphor is a general property of poetry. Furthermore, its incidence and complexity are more evident in the riddles than any other poetic genre. [1]

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THE PLACE OF ABBREVIATION IN MEDIA DISCOURSE

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МЕСТО АББРЕВИАТУРЫ В МЕДИАДИСКУРСЕ

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Abstract

The difference between "discourse analysis", "speech acts" and "text linguistics" is clarified by referring to the studies carried out in this field. The attention is drawn to different tendencies related to the topic. The article